

A Study on the Status of Free Essential Drug Services in the Primary Health Care Facilities of Kailali District, Nepal

Submitted to:

Department of Public Health

Central Institute of Science and Technology

New Baneshwor, Sangamchowk, Kathmandu, Nepal

Pokhara University

Submitted By:

Bipin Singh

Bachelor of Public Health

CiST College, December 2014

DECLARATION FORM

To the best of my knowledge and belief, I declare that this thesis entitled "*A Study on the Status of Free Essential Drug Service in the Health Facilities of Kailali Districts*" is the best of my own research and contains material previously published by any other person except where due acknowledgment has been made. This thesis contains no material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma in any university.

Signature:

Bipin Singh

Date.....

RECOMMENDATION

It is to be recommended that the research entitled "*A Study on the Status of Free Essential Drug Service in the Health Facilities of Kailali District*" is carried out by **Mr. Bipin Singh** for the partial fulfillment of **Bachelor of Public Health**. This original work was conducted under my full supervision. To the best of my knowledge, this dissertation work has not been submitted elsewhere for any other degree.

I would like to forward this research report for final evaluation.

APPROVAL LETTER

On the recommendation of the Dissertation Supervisor, Mr.Chiranjeebi Shah, this research report submitted by Bipin Singh entitled "*A Study on the Status of Free Essential Drug Service in the Health facilities of Kailali district*" is approved for examination and submission to Pokhara University in partial fulfillment of the requirements for Bachelor of Public Health.

Chiranjeebi Shah

Ram Bahadur Shrestha

Coordinator

Head of Department

Department of Public Health

Department of Public Health

CIST College

CIST College

Aff: Pokhara University

Aff: Pokhara University

Date:

Date:

CERTIFICATE OF EVALUATION

This research report entitled "*A Study on the Status of Free Essential Drug Service in the Health Facilities of Kailali District*" is "submitted by *Bipin Singh*, has been evaluated as a partial fulfillment of requirements for the Bachelor of Public Health.

EVALUATION COMMITTEE

External Examiner

Post:

Address:

Date.....

Chiranjeeb Shah

Dissertation Supervisor

Department of Public Health

CiST College

Date.....

Ram Bahadur Shrestha

Head of Department

Department of Public Health

CiST College

Date.....

Narayan Regmi

Associate Professor

Department of Public Health

CiST College

Date.....

Raj Kumar Subedi

Lecturer

Department of Public Health

CiST College

Date.....

Sushma Dahal

Lecturer

Department of Public Health

CiST College

Date.....

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research study entitled "A Study on the status of free essential drug service in the health facilities of Kailali district" is prepared as a partial fulfillment of the bachelor's in public health 4th-year curriculum of Pokhara University. Completion of a research study is never a matter of a single hand. It involves ample contribution at various levels and parts from many individuals who directly and indirectly contribute to the accomplishment of the research study. This is, therefore, an attempt to express my vote of thanks to the effort of all those hands that supported me through this entire novel path and helped me gain what I could never gain through my solitary effort.

Firstly, I am grateful to Pokhara University for including a research study under the curriculum of the BPH program. I would like to express my thanks to the Central Institute of Science and Technology (CIST) for providing the opportunity and supporting me to conduct this research study. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the Honorable Prof. Dr. B.D Chataut, principal of CIST College, for providing the opportunity and continuous support throughout the research period. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Mr. Ram Bahadur Shrestha, Head of Department and Department of Public Health, for his guardianship.

I would like to express profound gratitude to my dissertation supervisor, Mr.Chiranjeebi Shah, Coordinator of the Department of Public Health, CIST College, for guiding me to complete my dissertation. I am highly indebted to him for providing me with numerous useful and relevant materials required to complete this research and for being my constant inspiration and encouragement in the accomplishment of this arduous and challenging task.

I am equally grateful and would like to extend my profuse appreciation to Mr. Raj Subedi and Mrs.Sushma Dahal, lecturers of public health at CIST College. I would also like to thank Mr. Narayan Regmi CIST College, Mr. Baburam Humagain, and Dr. S.B Karki for their unfailing support and encouragement, which has undoubtedly inspired me to undertake this Herculean task.

I would like to express my sincere thanks and gratitude to Mr. Naveen Shrestha, Mrs. Saruna Ghimire, and Mr. Prakash Chandra Joshi for their continuous support from beginning to last.

Also like to express my profound respect and gratitude to them for being my constant source of inspiration and encouragement in the accomplishment of this arduous and challenging task.

Also, I would like to express my sincere thanks to the DPHO in charge of Kailali for the valuable support and help. I would also like to gratitude all the health institutions in charge who gave their valuable time and suggestions during the interview; the guidance provided by the staff was priceless. It is my pleasure to acknowledge and extend my sincere appreciation to all clients who participated in this study and helped me make my work successful.

I cannot resist expressing my acknowledgment to all my Colleagues at CIST College and my family members for their continual support and cooperation in times of difficulties. Also, I would like to express my acknowledgement to all my friends for their continuous support and co-operation during the entire research. I would also like to express gratitude to my parents, who always supported me in completing my dissertation. Last but not least, I would like to extend my thanks from the depth of my heart to all those well-wishers, friends, and supporters whose names might not have been mentioned but have helped me a great deal.

ABBREVIATION

BPH	Bachelor of Public Health
CDP	Community Drug Program
DH	District Hospital
DHO	District Health Office
DPHO	District Public Health Office
DRC	Development Resource Centre
EDL	Essential Drug List
ERC	Ethical Review Committee
FCHV	Female Community Health Volunteers
FEFO	First Expired First Out
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
FHCP	free Health Care Program
FIFO	First IN First Out
GESI	Gender Equality and Social Inclusion
GoN	Government of Nepal
HAI	Health Action International
HP	Health Post
KII	Key Informant Interview
LMD	Logistic Management Division

MOHP	Ministry of Health and Population
NEDLP	National Essential Drug List of Pakistan
PHCC	Primary Health Care Centers
RMS	Regional Medical Store
SDTS	Standard Drug Treatment Schedule
SHP	Sub Health Post
STP	Standard Treatment Protocol
VDC	Village Development Committee
WHO	World Health Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

On 15 December 2006, the Government of Nepal (GoN) made emergency and inpatient services free of charge at district hospitals and primary health care centers (PHCCs). Nepal's Existing health plan and policies and also the interim constitutions have expressed commitments to fulfilling the people's right in order to provide basic health services free of cost as stated by the law. As directed by Nepal's interim constitution, the Ministry of Health and Population (MOHP) is committed to providing free health services as defined in the free health care policy (FHCP). According to this policy, 25 essential drugs in SHPs, 35 essential drugs in HPs and PHCCs, and 40 essential drugs in up to 25 bedded hospitals should provided to clients free of cost.

The cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in order to assess the Status of free essential drug services in the primary health care facilities of the Kailali district. The study was conducted in the Kailali district. The study population of this study includes the primary health care facilities of Kailali district and patients visiting the health facilities for service. Altogether, 20 health facilities out of 41 were chosen by using systematic random sampling. From each 20 health facilities, 30 prescriptions were analyzed. The validity and reliability of the study tools were maintained by doing pretesting. The data was collected through an Interview and observation checklist. The data was collected and coded in an ordered manner and was entered in Epi-data 3.1, and analysis was done through SPSS version 22.

The study shows that 96.8% of people were aware of free drug services in the Kailali district. The percentage of females visiting the health facility was 53.3%, and for males was 46.7%. It was found that 74% of key essential drugs were available in the health facility of Kailali district. Also, the stock-out rate was found to be 26%. Although the drug program is free but still 1.5% of clients were paying for the service. The average number of drugs prescribed was found to be 2.95. The percentage of patient's encounters with antibiotics was 16%, and patients encountered with injections were found to be 6.76%. The percentage of drugs prescribed from the EDL was found to be 94.64%. Only 5% of patients with undiagnosed fever were treated according to the STP, and none of the patients encountered with Scabies were treated according to the STP. Similarly, 10% of patients with headaches and 16.6% of patients with abdominal pain were treated according to the STP.

The percentage of drugs actually dispensed from the health facility of Kailali district was found to be 99%, which reflects effective management of health facilities. The percentage of people who are extremely satisfied with the free drug program was 22.3%, very satisfied was 35.3%, and satisfied was 35.3%. Still, 7% of people were dissatisfied with this free drug program. It was found that in 15% of SHPs, 40% of HPs, and 50% of PHCCs, they had refrigerators to store drugs. Also, it was found that 58% of health facilities do not have the necessary backup in case of power failure. It was also found that 3% of drugs were kept past expiry in the health facilities of Kailali district.

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The interim constitution of Nepal (2007) enshrined health as a fundamental right of the citizens of Nepal. The Free care program is part of efforts to ensure this right and is designed to reduce morbidity and mortality by increasing access to health services, especially for poor, excluded, marginalized, remote, and vulnerable people.

The government of Nepal, the Department of Health Services, launched the Community Drug Program (CDP) in 1995 in an effort to ensure that 100% of essential drugs are available year-round in all health facilities by 2017 (DOHS 2062/2063 (2005/2006)). The program was functioning smoothly before the launching of the free healthcare program. However, very few districts are now continuing the CDP activities these days. (DOHS 2011-2012) On 15 December 2006, the Government of Nepal (GoN) made emergency and inpatient services free of charge at district hospitals and primary health care centers (PHCCs). The following five groups were targeted for free health services at district hospitals with up to 25 beds, according to the Free Health Service Implementation guidelines (DOHS 2064/2065 (2007/2008)).

1. Poorer (defined as able to provide adequate food for less than six months a year).
2. Poor (defined as able to provide adequate food for six to fewer than 12 months).
3. Destitute and disabled people.
4. Senior citizens (above 60 years of age)
5. Female community health volunteers (FCHVs) (Prasai, 2013)

On 7 October 2007, GoN declared that essential health care services were to be provided free of charge to all users at all health posts and sub-health posts (SHPs). Also, in 2008, all citizens became eligible for free care at health posts and sub-health posts. Similarly, in 2009, all citizens became eligible for selected essential drugs and delivery care. Targeted population groups (Poorer people, poor/destitute/helpless people, poor living with disabilities, senior citizens, and FCHVs) became eligible for all services at the district hospitals (up to 25 beds) free of charge. Free health service is in consonance with GoN's plans, policies, and strategies and is crucial in delivering basic health services to the targeted groups of people and the general people seeking

health services((DRC) 2012). At present, according to government policy, a range of services are provided free of charge for all citizens in public health facilities. These services include family planning, immunization, antenatal care, delivery care, postnatal care, integrated management of childhood illness, Tuberculosis, Leprosy, Malaria, Kala-azar, Lymphatic Filariasis, HIV/AIDS, and STD diagnosis and treatment.

In addition, outpatient consultations in the district hospital and lower-level health facilities and a range of listed essential drugs are also free. Some additional services are provided to specific population groups, including destitute people, poor people, people living with disabilities, senior citizens (60+ years), and FCHVs. As directed by Nepal's interim constitution, the Ministry of Health and Population (MOHP) is committed to providing free health services as defined in the free health care policy (FHCP). According to this policy, 25 essential drugs in SHPs, 35 essential drugs in HPs and PHCCs, and 40 essential drugs in up to 25 bedded hospitals should provided to clients free of cost((HSSP), Nepal et al. 2009)

The supply of essential drugs to different levels of health facilities is made through different channels. Of the total drug budget, LMD spends 70%, RHDs 10%, and DHO 20%. Funds are allocated to the district on the basis of drug utilization and facility-level morbidity status. The Logistics Management Division (LMD) also carries out procurement at the central level and sends drugs in bulk to Regional Medical Stores (RMS). The RMSs supply the drugs to the district as per central-level institutions. A stock of drugs is kept as a buffer in the District stores, and the rest is sent to facilities(Mehata, Lekhak et al. 2012).

Nepal's existing health plan and policies, as well as the interim constitutions, have expressed commitments to fulfilling the people's right to provide basic health services free of cost as stated by the law. However, the free drug program started in 2008 in a changed political context. It has targeted to support the general people as well as the special targeted groups. In particular with ultra poor, senior citizens, helpless, people living with disabilities, and FCHVs.

Currently, in Nepal, a hybrid model of push (central to regional medical store) and pull (district to regional medical store) exists. All the D(P)HOs distribute all the drugs to the HFs through the pull system (i.e., based on demand). A pull system of drug stocking at health facilities is a

demand-based approach for ensuring the reliable availability of drugs at service delivery points in a health system. DoHS introduced such a system in public health facilities around 2006. DoHS claims that the stock-out of essential drugs has been reduced from 31.9% in 2006/07 to 20.8% in 2010/11((DRC) 2012). The D(P)HOs receive demand for drugs from all the PHCCs, HPs, and SHPs through the pull system. At present, LMD has started multiyear procurement to address the delayed supply of free drugs. The GON has been investing a huge amount of budget to procure and supply essential drugs from the central, regional, and district levels in order to improve the health condition of the entire People. Ensuring the availability of sufficient quantities of drugs needed by patients remains a major challenge for Nepal's health system, and several studies have reviewed availability from both supplier and consumer perspectives. Access to essential drugs is a basic human right often denied to people in poor countries(HSSP), Nepal et al. 2009).

Common essential drugs are provided to all the SHPs, PHCCs, and district hospitals and have generally good effects, but some higher-level facilities, mainly referral facilities, require more advanced drugs((DRC) 2012). According to the MOHP, the current Status availability of essential healthcare services is about 78.83%, and the availability of free essential drugs is 93.3%. Also, the GON had made a three-year plan in order to increase the availability of essential health care services, which are provided free of cost from SHPs, HPs, PHCCs, and DH to 90%, and also to increase the availability of free essential drugs to 95%. Universal health coverage with quality of essential health care service free of cost. Quality drugs and other health-related materials and instruments will be made available in a systematic manner, and local industries and manufacturing companies will be given a chance and encouragement. Also, the quality of essential drugs and instruments for providing health services will be monitored according to the standard protocol(MOHP 2071).

1.2 Need Statement

The essential drug program under free health service has made significant progress in the last year in order to provide quality health services to all geographical regions, classes, genders, and ethnicities. Also, the free essential drug program has implemented GoN's plans, policies, and strategies in delivering basic health services to the general people seeking health services

from the PHCC, HP, and SHP. However, it was found that about two-thirds (67%) of patients visiting the health facilities received all the drugs prescribed by attending health workers, and (78%) reported that they received drugs free of cost. Still, a colossal proportion of patients did not get drugs as prescribed in the EDL. Similarly, it was found that about (92.5 % of Terai and Mountain and 95% of Hill) respondents were aware of the free drugs available at the HFs. Nearly half of the respondents (44 %) seemed very satisfied, 37% were satisfied, and still 11% were not satisfied with the current free drug program((DRC) 2012)

The GoN has already declared that all the health services at health posts (HPs), sub-health posts (SHPs), and Primary health care centers (PHCCs) are free of charge to all people as well as more easily accessible. Drugs should be prescribed as per the standard treatment protocol (STP) in order to provide quality health services. Whereas around 55% of the health workers used to prescribe 1 to 2 items of drugs, which account for 81% of Edl. Similarly, 40% of health workers prescribe 3 to 4 items of drugs, which account for only 19% of Edl. Also, it was found that the majority of health facilities used to dispense 67 percent of the medications, while 29 percent were partially dispensed, and 3 percent were not dispensed at all(International 2009).

The majority of health facilities face the problem of stocking out at least once a year. The most common drugs that were found to stock out were ferrous sulfate, folic acid, and amoxicillin at all primary healthcare facilities(Mehata, Lekhak et al. 2012). Also, around 60% of respondents were satisfied with the good quality of free essential drugs, and still, 19% were not satisfied with the quality of the free essential drugs provided by the primary health facilities. About 86% of the disadvantaged groups of people agreed that they had benefited from the free drug program, while 9% did not show their agreement(DRC) 2012).

The drug should be properly stored and adequately maintained in order to provide good quality services. An appropriate storage system is required to deliver effective and efficient health services. However, in many health facilities, stores are not well managed because too many staff members work in the store. It was found that a small percentage of PHHCs (3%), HP (1%), and SHPs (4%) kept drugs in an unlocked room. Likewise, 94% of PHCCs, 90% of HPs, and 85% of SHPs use to store drugs directly in the dry place. Furthermore, 19% of PHCCs, 8% of HPs, and 10% of SHPs store drugs directly on the floor. Whereas some drugs require

refrigeration in order to maintain cold-chain, only 58% of PHCCs, 35% of HPs, and 14% of SHPs were able to maintain cold-chain.

The GoN insists on a "first expiry, first out" system to control the storage of medicine in the health facilities. Around 75% of PHCCs, 74% of HPs, and 59% of SHPs follow the FEFO system, whereas 25% to 40% of health facilities still do not follow this system. The quality of drugs should be maintained and adequately checked, but it was found that many health facilities, like 48% of PHCCs, 54% of HPs, and 61% of SHPs, experienced problems with expired drugs in the last fiscal year(Mehata, Lekhak et al. 2012).

Drugs should be prescribed appropriately, and patients should be treated according to the Standard Treatment Protocol (STP). The average number of drugs prescribed per patient was found to be 2.2, and also the percentage of drugs prescribed from the EDL was 85.2%. Also, it was found that only 27.7% of patients received drugs according to the Standard Drug Treatment Schedule (SDTS)(kafle, pradhan et al. 1996). The study carried out in western Nepal reveals that only 90% of Primary healthcare facilities dispensed essential drugs fully, and, 10% of health facilities are unable to dispense them. It was also found that only 90% of key drugs were only available in the healthcare facilities(P, B et al. 2012).

There are several studies conducted in the Kailali district, but not a single study is carried out in a comprehensive manner. The free essential drug programs under the free health care service program have been facing many challenges in the primary health facilities of the Kailali district. Thus, this study intends to find out the quality, stock out, storage, and prescribing pattern and dispensing of prescribed drugs in the Primary health care facilities of Kailali district.

1.3 Objectives of the study

a. General Objective

To assess the Status of free essential drug services in the health facilities of Kailali district

b. Specific Objective

1. To identify the stock of essential drugs in health facilities

2. To find out the provision for storage of essential drugs
3. To analyze the prescribing pattern based on standard treatment protocol
4. To find out the Status of dispensed drugs as prescribed at health facilities
5. To identify the patient satisfaction towards free drug distribution program

1.4 Research question (s)

1. What is the Status of stock of essential drugs in health care facilities?
2. How the free essential drugs are stored in the health facilities?
3. Whether the prescribing pattern of essential drugs is according to the standard treatment protocol in health facilities or not?
4. Does the prescribed drug in health facility fully dispensed or not?
5. What is the level of satisfaction of people towards free drug distribution program?

1.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure:Conceptual framework

1.6 Study variables

The different type of variables regarding the study is given below:

Dependent Variables:

- Free essential drug service

Independent variables:

- Stock of essential drugs
- Storage
- Prescribing according to STP
- Satisfaction towards free drug
- Dispensed drugs as prescribed
- Perception regarding free essential drugs services

Socio-demographicvariables:

- Age
- Sex

1.7 Operational Definitions

- **Free essential drugs**

The free essential drugs refer to all the free drugs as described by the free health care policy which consist of 25 essential drugs in SHPs, 35 essential drugs HPs and PHCCs(Mehata, Lekhak et al. 2012).

- **Health facilities**

In this study health facility refers to the sub-health post, Health post and Primary health care centers.

- **Dispensed drug**

The dispensed drugs refer to the drugs which are actually given to the patients who visit health facilities for seeking treatment.

- **Standard treatment protocol**

The standard treatment protocol is the protocol developed by the Nepal government in order to treat the patients according to the certain standard(Revitalisation, Services et al. 2012).

- **Availability of drugs**

The availability of drugs refers to the accessible of essential drugs in the health facilities for one year duration.

- **Encounters**

It refers to the interactions with the patients who receive specific treatment from the health facilities.

- **Satisfaction**

Satisfaction is the extent to which general health care needs and condition-specific needs of the patients visiting the health facility for treatment are meet.

1.8 Limitations of the study

The limitation of this study could be the seasonal variance and fluctuation in the availability of essential drugs in the health facilities.

Chapter II: LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies in other countries

According to the cross-sectional study conducted in Uganda from 2006 to 2007, the percentage of essential drug out of stock in 2000 and 2001 period was 77.8% while in 2004 and 2005 period was reduced to 66.7%. Beside that the average percentage of days out of stock for essential drug was 15 days in 2001-2002 and was drastically reduced to 3.5 days in 2003-2004. The study concluded that the main hindrance factor behind availability of essential drugs was lack of transport and lack of funds to purchase drugs(Tumwine, Kutuyabami et al. 2010).

A baseline survey was conducted in Bangladesh on drug use at primary health care level using cross-sectional descriptive design. The drug use pattern and quality of care were assessed in 80 public health facilities in which total 2880 prescription, consultation, and drug-dispensing practices were studied. The study revealed that only 37% of the patients was adequately examined or treated as per the previously defined standard treatment guidelines (STG).The mean number of drug prescribed for an individual patient was found to be 1.44. Along with that 85% of drugs were prescribed from the essential drug list. In this study about 59% of patients were prescribed one drug, 36% of patients were prescribed two drugs and 5% of patients were prescribed three or more drugs. On an average only 81% of prescribed drugs were dispensed to the patients from the health facilities. On an average 54% of the health facilities had essential drug in stock(Guyon, Barman et al. 1994).

The mean number of drugs prescribed per patient was 2.76. Also all the drugs prescribed were included in the essential drug list. Around 6.7% prescription were not according to the standard treatment protocol (STP)(Pati 2004).

The cross sectional prospective-descriptive study was conducted in India in order to assess the drug dispensing practices using who patient care and health facility indicator for six months. The study population consists of 100 OPD patients. In this study the percentage of drug actually dispensed from the health facilities was 95.54%.Where as, the availability of the key essential drugs in the health facility was found to be only 91.67 %(MATHEW, GADDE et al. 2013).

A randomized sample survey was done in Pakistan in order to audit the prescribing practices of consultants. About 354 prescriptions were analyzed on the basis of parameters recommended by the world health organization (WHO). The average number of drug

prescribed per patient was found to be 4.51. Also it was found that the number of essential drug prescribed from National Essential drug list of Pakistan (NEDLP) was only 49.81(Das, Baloch et al. 2006).

A study was conducted in 2004 in Islamic Republic of Iran in order to evaluate the prescribing, dispensing, availability and affordability of drug in 100 primary health care centers using WHO indicators. The study reveals that 92% of essential drugs were available in the health facility.

On an average 95% of essential drugs prescribed by the health worker were actually dispensed by the health facility. The quality of drug storage get 8 scored which was assessed by using scale with lowest score 0 to highest score 11. Similarly, the average number of drug prescribed per individual patient was 3.4. Also it was found that very fewer percentages of prescriptions followed the National standard treatment guideline i.e. 12% of prescription followed STG for treatment of uncomplicated diarrhea(Cheraghali, Nikfar et al. 2004).

A descriptive retrospective study was conducted in Nigerian tertiary hospital in order to assess the prescribing pattern of the clinicians. The study was conducted by analyzing 497 prescriptions between April and July 2009. It was found that on an average 3.04 drugs were prescribed for an individual patient. It was also found that 94% drugs were prescribed from the essential drug list (EDL). The key drug availability at the time of dispensing was found to be 91.7%(Tamuno and Fadare 2012).

A cross-sectional study was carried out in 2009 in the Southwest Ethiopia by randomly selecting four health facilities. Retrospectively 35 prescriptions from each four health facilities were analyzed by using WHO indicators. This study shows different result obtains from four different health facilities. The average number of drug prescribed per individual patients in four different health facilities was found to be (2.88, 2.10, 1.91, and 1.80). Similarly, the percentage of drug prescribed from EDL was (89.37%, 91.85%, 89.09%, and 90.81%). The percentage of drug actually dispensed from health facilities was (77.22%, 89.04%, 89.55% and 77.77%). Also the percentage of availability of key drugs in stock was found to be (66.76%, 60%, 53.33% and 80%)(Angamo, Wabe et al. 2011)

A cross-sectional descriptive study involving both qualitative and quantitative approach was conducted in 2009 in Ghana. The general objective of this study was to determine the

availability and affordability of essential medicine by incorporating World Health Organization and health Action International (WHO and HAI) methodology. The study found that means availability of essential drugs in health facility was 64.1 % (Nyanwura and Esena 2013).

Studies in Nepal

The stock out rate was found to be 29% in the health facilities. It was also found that there were no stock out of key drugs including contraceptives pills, ORS package, ferrous sulphate tablet, cotrimaxazole, albendazole and paracetamol (HSSP), Nepal et al. 2009).

A prospective cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted in 11 Primary health care facilities of Kaski district using WHO core drug use indicator. A total of 301 prescriptions were analyzed in order to assess the drug use pattern in health facilities. The study found out that the average number of drug prescribed per individual patient was 2.29. Similarly, the percentage of drug prescribed from the essential drug list was about 85.19%. It was also found that 89.63% of free essential drugs were only dispensed from the health facilities. The study also reveals that the total percentage of availability of key essential drugs on the health facility was found to be only 89.69 % (P, B et al. 2012)

A study was conducted in the primary healthcare facilities of the Terai district, which comprises 36 health posts and 27 sub-health posts. In this study drug prescribing and dispensing practices were assessed by using WHO indicators. On an average 30 prescription from total 63 health facility were collected and analyzed. The study reveals that on an average 2.2 drugs were prescribed per individual patients. Around 85.2% of drugs were found to be prescribed from EDL and only 81% of prescribed drugs were dispensed from health institutions. While only 27.7% of drugs were prescribed in accordance with standard drug treatment schedule (SDTS). The average drug prescription per individual in Kailali district was found to be 2. While in the Kailali district 84.70% prescribed drugs were actually dispensed from the health facility. Moreover only 83.50% of essential drugs were prescribed from the EDL. The percentage of drug prescribed in accordance with SDTS was around 37.40% in Kailali (Kafle, Pradhan et al. 1996).

Development Resource Centre (DRC) conducted the evaluation on essential drug procurement and distribution program under the free health care service. The evaluation was done by

incorporating cross-sectional study design based on mixed methodology which comprises of both quantitative and qualitative methods. A total 78 HFs were observed in which 100 interviews, 15 FGD, 30 key informant interviews were conducted. The study found that about 67% of patients received the entire drug prescribed by the health workers. The study also concluded that 16.6% of HFs from the mountain, 52.2% of HFs from the terai, and 57% of HFs from the hill region had round-the-year drug availability. Whereas 80% HFs from the mountain, 43% from the hill, and 52% from terai face the problem of stock out of at least one essential drug in the last fiscal year. While 78% of patients receive drugs free of cost, and 22% of patients have to pay for the drug((DRC) 2012).

The service tracking survey (STS) was conducted in 2012 in order to monitor the different indicators of NHSP-II, Aama program, and free care Aama program, quality of care, and to collect information related to gender equality and social inclusion (GESI). This survey assesses the different indicators of free healthcare services, including free drug programs. It was found that a small percentage of PHHCs (3%), HP (1%), and SHPs (4%) use to keep drugs in an unlocked room. Likewise 94% of PHCCs, 90% HPs and 85% SHPs use to store drugs directly in the dry place. Furthermore, 19% of PHCCs, 8% of HPs, and 10% of SHPs stores drugs directly on the floor. Whereas some drugs require refrigeration in order to maintain cold-chain only 58% of PHCCs, 35% of HPs, and 14% of SHPs were able to maintain cold-chain.

The GoN insists on a "first expiry, first out" system to control the storage of medicine in the health facilities. Around 75% of PHCCs, 74% of HPs, and 59% of SHPs follow the FEFO system, whereas 25% to 40% of health facilities still do not follow this system. Also, it was found that many health facilities, like: 48% of PHCCs, 54% of HPs, and 61% of SHPs, experienced problems with expired drugs in the last fiscal year. This survey provides key information about drug supply and storage at different level of health facilities. The percentage of facilities with drugs stored as per first expired, first out (FEFO) principles was only 84.4%(Mehata, Lekhak et al. 2012).

CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study design

The study design was a cross-sectional descriptive study.

3.2 Study site and its justification

The study was conducted in the Kailali district which was selected purposively. Also this district is ranked in 46th position in HDI out of 75.

3.3 Study population

The study population consists of all the health facilities of the Kailali district and also the patients visiting the health facilities for service.

3.4 Sampling Procedure and sample size

The sampling technique used was systematic random sampling for the selection of the 10 Health posts, 2 Primary health care centers, and 8 sub-health posts.

The sample size estimated for this study was obtained by using the following procedures:

Type of HFs	PHCC	HP	SHP	Total
Current HFs	4	20	17	41
Proportion (p) at 95% C.I	0.097	0.487	0.414	
HFs to be choose	$0.097*20= 1.94$	$0.487*20=9.74$	$0.414*20= 8.28$	20

In order to draw valid conclusion it is necessary to select representative sample. Moreover, 30 patients encounter was chosen from each 20 health facility and if the required patients encounter didn't reach at that time all the patients visiting the health facility was chosen(WHO 1993). The patients first in health facility for check up were chosen until the desired encounter i.e. 30. Finally 2 PHCCs and 10 HPs were chosen by using systematic random sampling.

3.5 Tools and techniques of data collection

Techniques: Observation, interview

Tools: Observation checklist, interview guideline

3.6 Validity and reliability of tools

In order to make the study tools reliable and valid, it was pretested in the Godavari health post prior to the study which was not included in my study unit. Finally necessary correction was made based on their feedback. Also, respondents were encouraged to provide reliable information. WHO indicators and standard treatment protocol for health posts and sub-health posts developed by GON were strictly followed. Also, the questionnaire was translated in Nepali for convenience. Also some of the questionnaire was taken from the service tracking survey conducted in 2012 by Dr. Suresh Mehata, et al.

3.7 Data collection procedure

Before starting the interview, informed consent was taken in written form for both literate and illiterate, but in the case of the illiterate one, it was taken in the presence of a literate eyewitness. Then, the data was collected by using structured and semi-structured questionnaires and also through the observation checklist. Basically, the patient visiting the health facility for the health service was interviewed to collect desired information. Also information was collected through the observation checklist.

3.8 Data management (entry, analysis, and interpretation)

The data was collected and coded in an ordered manner for convenient entry and identification. The data was entered in Epi-data version 3.11 and was transferred to SPSS version 22 for data analysis. The data analyzed was presented by the use of charts, graphs, and descriptions.

3.9 Ethical consideration

In order to maintain the ethical consideration in this study, at first this proposal was submitted to the Ethical Review Committee (ERC) of CIST College and after its final approval the study was carried out in Kailali district of Nepal. Moreover, informed consent was taken from the (DPHO). Finally, the informed consent was taken from the participants of this study.

Chapter IV- Findings

The general objective of the study is to assess the Status of free essential drug service in the health facilities of Kailali district. Study content questionnaire for clients who visit health institution for their health problems along with observation checklist for health institutions.

Findings from exit client interview (N=600)

4.1 Socio-demographic characteristics:

Table below represent the information on the socio-demographic characteristic of the respondents, which include age and sex of the respondents.

The figure below shows the distribution of sex; among all of the 600 respondents, 280 were male and 320 were female, which accounts for 46.7 and 53.3 percent, respectively. The male-female ratio among all respondents was 1:1.14

Regarding the age, most of the respondents were of young age i.e. of 6-15. The lowest age and highest age of respondents were 0 years and 82 years, respectively. The highest age categories of respondents were found to be between 6 years to 15 years, i.e., 24.2%.

Table 1 Socio-demographic Characteristics

Category	Frequency N=600	Percentage P=100
Age		
<=5	102	17

6-15	145	24.2
16-25	122	20.3
26-35	94	15.7
36-45	41	6.8
46-55	31	5.2
>=60	65	10.8
Sex		
Male	280	46.7
Female	320	53.3

4.2 Knowledge regarding the free drug program

This chart deals with the analysis of the knowledge about the free drug program service provided by the Nepal Government. This section gives emphasis on whether people knew about free drug program services provided by the government from primary health facilities in order to achieve the goal of health for all. This analysis was based on the findings drawn from the exit client interview who visited a health institution. This finding shows that 96.80% have knowledge about the free drug programs, in the same way, 3.20% don't know about the free drug programs.

Figure 1 Knowledge regarding free drug program

4.3 Provision for payment for free drug received from health facility

This figure explains whether the people have to pay for the free drug received from the health facility or not. It was found that only 1.5% of people have paid for the free drug and rest of the 98.5% did not paid yet all. Few people have paid for the free drug from which ranges from 25 rupees to maximum 400 rupees.

Figure 2 Payment for free drug received from HFs

4.4 Satisfaction with free drug program

The figure below shows the clients satisfaction and dissatisfaction towards the free drug program. These shows (35%) of clients were very satisfied with this free drug program while that of 7% client were dissatisfied. Also the percentage of clients very satisfied with free drug program was found to be 36%.

Figure 3 Satisfaction with free drug program

4.5 Provider response to stock out of drug included under free drug policy (N=20)

This figure explains provider's response when the drugs get out of stock. Commonly (48%) clients were told to buy the drugs themselves. Similarly (27.5%) of clients were told to come next day for drug when the drugs get out of stock on the day of visit. Whereas, only (20.5%)

of clients were provided with similar type of drugs.

Figure 4 Provider response to stock out of drug

4.6 Diagnosis mentioned in the prescriptions of the encountered patients (N=600)

This figure reveals the top10 diseases mentioned in the prescription encountered by the clients. Most of the patients were suffered from fever i.e. (18%) followed by conjunctivitis (12%) and

(3%) from ARI and allergy. It was also seen that most of the patients suffered from communicable diseases rather than non-communicable diseases.

Figure 5 Diagnosis mentioned in the prescriptions of the encountered patients

4.7 Drugs prescribed from the essential drug list along with antibiotic and injections (N=600)

This table describes the percentage of drugs actually prescribed from the essential drug list. It also explains the percentage of antibiotics and injections prescribed according to health facilities. It was found that in PHCC (92%), Hp (94%), and SHP (97%) drugs were prescribed from the EDL. Whereas the percentage of antibiotics prescribed from PHCC, HP, and SHP was found to be (18%), (16%) and (14%) respectively. Similarly, the antibiotic prescription was found to be high (8%) in PHCC, (7%) in HP, and (5%) in SHP.

Table 2 Percentage of drugs prescribed from the essential drug list along with antibiotic and injections

	PHCC (%)	HP (%)	SHP (%)	Total (%)
Drug prescribed from EDL	92	94	97	94.6
Prescription containing antibiotic	18	16	14	16
Prescription containing injection	8	7	5	6.6

4.8 Drugs actually dispensed from the health facility

This figure explains that 99% of prescribed drugs were actually dispensed from the health institutions whereas only 1% of drugs were not fully dispensed. For not dispensed drugs patients were informed to buy from nearby private clinic or advice to come next day.

Figure 6 : Percentage of drugs actually dispensed from health facility

4.9 Patients treated according to STP

This table explains the prescribing practices of health workers in the health facilities of Kailali district. It was found that very high percentages of patients with different diseases were not treated according to standard treatment protocol (STP). Only 5% of patients with undiagnosed fever were treated according to STP, and none of the patients were treated according to STP in the case of Scabies. Similarly, it was also seen that the majority of patients were not treated according to the standard treatment protocol.

Table 3 Patients treated according to STP

Diseases treated according to STP	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
Undiagnosed fever	108	5
Headache	42	10
Gastritis	22	13
Scabies	8	0
Worm infestation	6	16.6

Findings from observation of health institutions: (N=20)

4.10 Availability of free essential drugs in health facilities

Observational findings of health institutions revealed that only 74% of essential drugs were stock in the health institutions. Meanwhile, about 26% of essential drugs were out of stock in health facilities. Only albendazole, amoxicillin tablets, compound solution of sodium lactate (Ringer lactate), metronidazole, and paracetamol tablets were available in all the health institutions.

Figure 7 Availability of free essential drugs in health facilities

4.11 Availability of free essential drugs according to health facility (N=20)

As explained in the above figure, the availability of essential drugs is not satisfactory. Only in the SHP, 80% of drugs were available on the day of the visit, and in HP and PHCC, only 70% and 74% of drugs were available. Stock The outrate of essential drugs seems to be higher in Health post and primary health care centers than in sub-health post.

Figure 8 Availability of drugs according to health facility

4.12 Expired drugs stored

The diagram below indicates the drugs that were most likely to be stored past expiry during the time of the visit. It was found that (3%) of drugs were most likely to be stored past the expiry date. The drugs that were stored past expiry include Albendazole, Amoxiciline tablet, Gentamycin injection, Metronidazole, povidone-iodine solution, pheniramine injections, and ciprofloxacin ointment.

Figure 9 Drugs most likely to be stored past expiry date

4.13 Experience of stock-outs of essential drugs

This figure shows the percentage of health facilities facing stock-out problems in Kailali district. Most of the facilities reported experiencing stock-outs during the day of the visit. It was found that charcoal-activated powder was found to be stocked in all the health facilities of the Kailali district. Similarly, pheniramine injection, promethazine tab, sodium chloride injection, and atropine injection were most commonly stocked out in the Kailali district.

Figure 10 Stock out of free essential drugs

4.14 Place for drug storage (N=20)

This table illustrates the different places for drug storage in the health facilities of Kailali district. It was found that none of the health facilities stored drugs in damp/water areas;

similarly, all the health facilities stored drugs in dry and raised platforms in a proper manner. Whereas, (20%) of health facilities had stored drugs in a place where there was direct exposure to sunlight. Also, (90%) of health institutions in the Kailali district stored drugs on shelves and locked cabinets. It was found that most of the health facilities of Kailali district stored drugs in a locked room or space, i.e. (95%) and very few, i.e. (5%) of health facilities stored in unlocked rooms or space

Figure 11 Place for drug storage

4.15 Storage of drug in FEFO approach

This figure explains that most of the health facilities in Kailali district use to keep drugs in the FEFO approach. In order to prevent misuse (85%) of health facilities use to store drugs in the FEFO approach. Whereas only (10%) of health facilities did not follow this approach.

Figure 12 Storage of drug in FEFO approach

4.16 Storage of drugs in (FEFO) approach by facility level

As explained in the above figure, most of the health facilities followed the FEFO approach to store drugs; here, it shows which type of health facility keeps most of the drugs in this approach. Mostly, all the PHHCs in the Kailali district store drugs in the FEFO approach, and (25%) of the sub-health posts did not follow this approach completely.

Table 4 Storage of drugs in (FEFO) approach by facility level

	PHCCs (%)	HP (%)	SHP (%)
All	0.0	40	37.5
Most	100	50	25
Some	0.0	0.0	12.5
None	0.0	0.0	25
Cannot be observed	0.0	10	0.0
Total facilities (N)	2	10	8

4.17 Availability of refrigerators by health facilities

Refrigerators were only available in 60% of health facilities in the Kailali district. While the rest of the others use ice-box in order to maintain the cold chain. Mainly (50%) of PHCCs, (40%) of HPs, and (15%) of SHPs have refrigerators in order to maintain cold-chain.

Figure 13 Availability of refrigerator by health facilities

4.18 Temperature of functional refrigerator

This figure explains the temperature of the functional refrigerator. Most of the refrigerators were found to be operated under an appropriate temperature range from (2 to 8 degrees Celsius).

Figure 14 Temperature of functional refrigerator

4.19 Power failure backup for refrigerator

This chart shows that only 42% of functional refrigerators had inverters for power failure backup. So, these health facilities maintained appropriate temperatures for 24 hours. Where 58% of functional refrigerators lack the necessary backup in case of power failure. So at the time of power cut off this refrigerator will fail to maintain the appropriate temperature.

Figure 15 Power failure backup for refrigerator

DISCUSSION

WHO core drug use indicator was used in this study in order to assess the Status of free essential drugs in health facilities. The demographic details of patients visiting the health facilities show (53.3%) female and (46.7%) male. The male-female ratio was found to be 1:1.14. Also, the age group of patients mainly visiting the health facilities was from the age group of 6 years to 25 years, i.e. (44.5%).

The average drug prescribed was found to be 2.95, which seems to be greater than the past studies conducted in Nepal, i.e. 2.29(P, B et al. 2012) and 2.2(kafle, pradhan et al. 1996). Similarly the study conducted in eight developing countries shows wide variation in average drug prescribing which ranges from 1.44 in Bangladesh(Guyon, Barman et al. 1994) and 4.51 in Pakistan(Das, Baloch et al. 2006). In this study, the average drug prescribed was found to be greater than the WHO guideline on rational use of drug, which ranges from 1.6-1.8(Tamuno and Fadare 2012).

The percentage of drug encounters with antibiotics was found to be 16%, which is lower than the WHO reference value of 20.0-25.4%(Tamuno and Fadare 2012). It is,, however,, lower than the figures reported by studies done in Bangladesh(25%)(Guyon, Barman et al. 1994), Iran(58%)(Cheraghali, Nikfar et al. 2004), Uzbekistan(43%)(Pavin, Nurgozhin et al. 2003), Ethiopia (25.5%)(Angamo, Wabe et al. 2011) , and Nigeria(34.4%)(Tamuno and Fadare 2012). Thus, it was reported to be lower than the previous study conducted in Nepal, which was (57%)(P, B et al. 2012). Inappropriate use of antibiotics leads to antimicrobial resistance. also, it may require more expensive and higher doses of antibiotics in order to treat simple forms of disease.

In this study, injection use was found in 6.76% of encounters. The percentage of injections prescribed was less than the one of the previous study conducted in Nepal, which was (13.7%)(kafle, pradhan et al. 1996) and greater than the other study conducted in Nepal, which was (3%)(P, B et al. 2012). However, much higher value of injection use was reported from various studies, like in Iran(41%)(Cheraghali, Nikfar et al. 2004), in Pakistan(37.28%)(Das, Baloch et al. 2006), in Uzbekistan(28.7%)(Pavin, Nurgozhin et al. 2003) , and in Ethiopia (38%)(Desalegn 2013).

The percentage of drugs prescribed from EDL was found to be more satisfactory than the other previous studies conducted in Nepal, which were (85.9%)(P, B et al. 2012) and (85.2%)(Kafle, Pradhan et al. 1996). The percentage of drugs prescribed from EDL was similar to the study conducted in Nigeria(94%)(Tamuno and Fadare 2012). Variation in the drug prescribed from EDL was reported in a study conducted in Pakistan(50%)(Das, Baloch et al. 2006) and in Ethiopia (96.6%)(Desalegn 2013).

The percentage of drugs actually dispensed was 99%. The study conducted in Nepal showed that (89.63%) drugs were dispensed(P, B et al. 2012). The study conducted in Bangladesh showed that only (81%) of drugs were dispensed. Also, the study conducted in Iran showed (95%) drugs were dispensed. Drug dispensed in the health facility of Kailai district was excellent. When there is a higher percentage of drugs dispensed, it reflects effective and efficient management of health institutions.

The availability of key essential drugs was 74%. The previous study conducted in Nepal showed 89.69% of drug availability in health facilities(PB et al. 2012). Development Resource Centre conducted a study on the evaluation of the Essential Drug Procurement and Distribution Program under Free Health Services shows that 20.9% of the drugs were out of stock in health facilities(DRC) 2012). Also, the study conducted in Nigeria showed (91.7%) of drugs were available in health facilities. Whereas, a study conducted in Ghana showed 64.1%(Nyanwura and Esena 2013) and in Bangladesh showed (63%) drug availability in the health facilities, which was found to be lower than this study. The drug stockout rate was found to be 26%. Also, the study conducted in Uganda showed (66.7%) of drugs were out of stock.

A review of studies of Nepal's national free health care program shows that 69% of people were satisfied with the free drug program(prasai 2013). However, in this study, 22.3% of clients were extremely satisfied, 35.3% were very satisfied, and 35.3% were satisfied with the free drug program. Development Resource Centre conducted a study on the evaluation of the Essential Drug Procurement and Distribution Program under Free Health Services and revealed that about 81% of people were satisfied with the current free drug service(DRC) 2012).

It was found that 96.8% of people were only aware of the free drug programs, while 3.2% were still unknown. The result seems to be more satisfactory than the past studies conducted, which

was only 93% (DRC) 2012). Most of the people in the Kailali district were aware of the free drug program.

The percentage of drugs kept in a locked room or space was found to be 95%, which was lower than the past study conducted in Nepal, which was 96.77%((DRC) 2012). Also, 20% of drugs were kept in direct exposure to sunlight, and all the health facilities kept drugs in raised platforms and in dry places.

The percentage of drugs stored past expiry was 3%. The study conducted in Iran shows(0.7%) of drugs were out of stock(Cheraghali, Nikfar et al. 2004). A past study conducted in Nepal shows that 22.6% of PHCCs, 32.9% of HPs, and 33.33% of SHPs were most likely to keep past expiry drugs(Mehata, Lekhak et al. 2012). The percentage of drugs stored past expiry was higher than the study conducted in Iran and lower than the study conducted in Nepal by service tracking survey 2012.

CONCLUSION

Most of the people of Kailali district were aware of the free drug service. Despite being a free drug program, still, 1.5% percent of people are paying for it. The availability of key drugs was only in 74% of health facilities, which indicates 26% of stock out of drugs. The provider advises clients to purchase drugs privately at the time of stock out of the drug. Also, the drug actually dispensed from the health facilities was excellent. About 99% of prescribed drugs were fully dispensed. This reflects the effective management of the health institutions. Whereas only 94.64% of drugs were only prescribed from the essential drug list. Only 5% of patients with undiagnosed fever were treated according to the STP and none of the patients encountering Scabies were treated according to the STP. Similarly, 10% of patients with headaches and 16.6% of patients with abdominal pain were treated according to the STP.

The stockout rate of the drugs was 26%, and charcoal was stocked out in every health institution in the Kailali district. Similarly, pheniramine injections, promethazine tablets, and Sodium chloride injections were mostly stocked out in the Kailali district. Also, it was seen that 3% of total drugs were kept past expiry. Only 85% of health institutions of Kailali district follow the FEFO approach, which may be due to the practice of keeping drugs past expiry. The practice of storing drugs in a locked room was satisfactory.

The availability of refrigerators was only in 15% of SHP, 40% of Hp, and 50% of PHCCs of Kailali district. Most of the functional refrigerator was operated under appropriate temperatures, and there was no necessary provision seen in 58% of health institutions during power failure.

RECOMMENDATION

- D/PHO should provide drugs timely with the required amount of drugs
- D/PHO should frequently monitor whether the patients have to pay unusual amounts for free drug services or not
- Healthcare providers should prescribe drugs according to standard treatment protocol
- Reduce stock-outs by more effectively implementing the pull system of drug management at health facilities
- Every health facility should try to keep drugs in the FEFO approach
- The expiry date of the drug should be checked and disposed of properly in case of expiry
- All Health facilities should keep drugs in a locked room and should not expose them directly to sunlight
- Health facilities should keep drugs in refrigerators in order to maintain cold-chain

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ANNEX

Informed consent Format

Hello. My name is Bipin Singh, and I am studying for a bachelor's in public health at the Central Institute of Science And Technology in the 8th semester. I am conducting research on the "Status of free essential drugs in primary health facilities of Kailali district of Nepal "and would appreciate your participation. I would like to ask you some questions regarding free essential drugs. This information will help us determine the status of free essential drugs. This interview will usually take 10 minutes to complete. Whatever information you provide will be kept strictly confidential and will not be shown to other persons.

Participation in this survey is voluntary, and you can choose not to answer any individual question or all of the questions. However, we hope that you will participate in this exit client interview.

Since your views are important.

At this time, do you want to ask me anything about the Study?

- Signature of participant: _____ Date_____

Observation Checklist

Location.....

Investigator.....

Date.....

S.N	Name of essential drugs	Availability of drugs		Expiration Time/months
		0= No	1= Yes	
A.	For Sub Health Posts (SHPs)			
1	Albendazole Tab			
2	Aluminium Hydroxide + Magnesium hydroxide Tab.			
3	Amoxyciline Tab, cap.			
4	Calamine lotion			
5	Chloramphenicol Applicaps			
6	Chlorpheniramine Tab.			
7	Ciprofloxacin Drops			
8	Ciprofloxacin Ointment			
9	Clove Oil			
10	Compound solution of sodium lactate (Ringer lactate) Inj.			
11	Ferrous salt + folic acid Tab.			
12	Gamma benzene hexachloride cream			
13	Getntamycin Inj.			
14	Hyoscinebutylbromide Tab.			
15	Lignocaine Inj.			
16	Magnesium sulphate Inj.			
17	Metoclorpropamide Inj.			
18	Metronidazole Tab., Sus.			
19	ORS powder			
20	Oxytocin Inj.			

21	Paracetamol Tab., Inj., syp.		
22	Pheniramine Inj.		
23	Povidinelodine Solution		
24	Sulfamethoxazole + Trimethoprim Tab., Sus.		
25	Vitamin B complex Tab.		
B.	For PHCCS and health posts (HPs)		
26	Atenolol Tab.		
27	Atropine Inj.		
28	Benzoic acid + Salicylic acid cream		
29	Charcoal activated powder		
30	Ciprofloxacin Tab.		
31	Dexamethasone Inj.		
32	Frusemide Tab.		
33	Promethazine Tab.		
34	Salbutamol Tab		
35	Sodium chloride Inj.		

Provision for Storage of Drug

1. Storage of drugs

a. In a locked room or space

b. In a unlocked room or space

2. Place of drug storage

S.N	Places for drug storage	0= No	1= Yes
1	Directly on the floor		
2	On a raised platform		
3	On shelves		
4	In a locked cabinet		
5	In a unlocked cabinet		
6	Exposed to direct sunlight		
7	Stored in cool place		
8	Exposed to damp/water		
9	Stored in dry place		

3. Availability of refrigerator to store all drugs that required cold chain:

a) Yes

b) No

4. If yes then number of functional refrigerators:

- a) 1 b) 2 c) 3 d) 4+ e)None

5. Storage place of drugs that require cold- chain where refrigerator is not available:

- a) Use of ice box (i) yes (ii) No b) Others
.....specify

6. Storage of drugs in First Expired First out (FEFO) approach:

- a) All b) Most c) Some d) None e) Cannot be
observed

7. Power failure back up.....

8. Temperature of refrigerator

Patients encounter form

Name & type of facility		Name & type of facility	
Diagnosis		Diagnosis	
Age/Sex		Age/Sex	
Name of medicine	Dispensed drugs fully 1= Yes 0=No	Name of medicine	Dispensed drug fully 1=Yes 0=No

Work Plan (Gantt chart)

		August, 2014	September, 2014				Oct, 2014		November, 2014				December, 2014	
S.N	Activities	Last week	2 nd week	3 rd week	4 th week	3 rd week	4 th week	1 st week	2 nd week	3 rd week	4 th week	1 st week	2 nd week	
1.	Topic Selection													
1.	Submission of Research proposal to NHRC, literature review													
2.	Data collection													
3.	Data entry													
4.	Data analysis and literature review													
5.	Preparation for report and presentation slides													